

EFFECTIVE PERSONALIZATION IN BLENDED LEARNING

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7590956>

ELSEVIER

Received: 22-01-2023

Accepted: 22-01-2023

Published: 22-01-2023

Komilova M.O
senior teacher of TMA
Kholmurodova L.D
student of TMA
khlola2110@gmail.com

Abstract: article reveals the effectiveness and availability of personalized learning of medical students, which provides maximum involvement in the leaning process.

Keywords: online resources, technology, control, pace, dynamics, personalization, digital tools, website, lecture, group discussions, online discussion

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

This year has given the world a huge shift in the need to develop and take advantage of blended learning. Alternative technological approaches to learning have come with challenges, but also with huge innovations. This is an exciting time for blended learning to grow and expand.

In the era of digital learning, mixed online and offline learning modes are defined as certain learning modes that combine contact learning with teachers and self- study using online resources. [9] Thus, the current study considers this as a working definition of mixed online and offline teaching of pedagogical disciplines, as it reveals the nature of a mixed mode, that is, mixed learning that can improve the quality of education, allow medical students to study pedagogy more excitingly and actively and promote their involvement in the study of disciplines. [1]

Blended learning: a combination of technology and personal learning. It combines regular group learning with online learning, and students have some control over the time, pace and place of their study.

There are several reasons for the transition from the classical form of education to blended. In higher educational institutions, this is primarily due to the widespread trend towards the optimization of processes at the end of the 20th century. Blended learning has proven to be significantly more effective than learning entirely online. This study significantly strengthened the position of blended learning and gave even greater dynamics to its development. [2] Blended learning for medical students is relatively new.

Blended learning in pears can be a powerful method to more effectively personalize the learning of medical students. But diving into blended learning can be overwhelming, and it can be hard to even decide where to start. [8] It is

important to understand exactly what blended learning and, as a result, personalized learning are, and how they are related. While there are many definitions for these terms in the educational technology industry, we think these definitions are a good place to start:

Personalization: student and educator collaborate to stimulate learning and identify needs, plan and design learning plan. Success factor in blended learning is the personalization of the educational process that allow students to build an individual educational trajectory and learn at their own pace, that is, this is the provision of a certain right to the student himself to choose which way, when, how and to some extent, "what" he will do.

The personalization of education is aimed not only at realizing the uniqueness and value of one's own "I", but also at creating conditions for the formation of a personal need to share one's knowledge and experience of its application with others. In general, the personalization of education combines a student-centered approach to differentiation and individualization of learning, which is used in formal education, with a socialized consideration of self-education in informal interactions - face to face and virtually.

The result of personalized education for the individual is education as a value, and for society and the state, as an integral, but assessed and measurable potential for the education of each person and individual communities and categories of the population.

Personalization of a student in the process of studying at the university means his self-determination in his chosen profession and willingness to participate in joint educational and social events as a partner who is ready to help others with his specific knowledge and experience. The work takes into account the relationship of personalization, personification and individualization in the educational process of higher education.

Personalization is closely related to the personality and individuality of the student.,"Personalized" medical student, prefers to independently determine the line of his behavior. In the context of globalization, with high growth rates of information and cultural resources, he seeks to maintain autonomy and independence in building his personal life. Personalized model of educational environment raises the autonomy of personality of the student.

At the heart of personalized learning lying the understanding of how important it is to be able to choose the most interesting or relevant educational material for yourself, identify a medical student and adjust the pace of learning to your regime, that is, adapt learning to your needs and abilities, and not adhere to a certain rigid structure of the educational course.

At the moment, there are at least three approaches that allow you to respond flexibly to the characteristics and needs of the student. These approaches include personalized learning (personalization), individualized learning and adaptive learning.

Personalized learning (personalization) is learning in which the student has the opportunity to choose the content (from the proposed), pace, and in some cases the place of study and the format of tasks based on their learning goal, personal characteristics and interests, as well as the recommendations of the electronic system and/or teacher. In personalized learning, the criteria for learning success are primarily determined by the achievement of the goal or goals of the student, and only then by the achievement of the goal or goals of the curriculum. In other words, the student can determine the goal of learning for himself and choose from the proposed learning content necessary to achieve it, based on the recommendations. If during the learning process the student's goal changes, this may lead to the choice of a different content (lessons) from the proposed ones.

Blended learning is a modality of learning. Blended learning is educational program in which the student is studying:

- partly online, with some element of student control of time, place, path and/or pace,
 - partly in an educational institution with a teacher away from home
 - and the ways of teaching each student within the course or subject are connected,
- to provide an integrated learning experience.

Personalized education is a broad term. But within this discussion, personalized education seeks to embrace a variety of methods, approaches and models, which adapts learning and development to the individual student. They tend to reinforce a clear philosophy about how we can help students achieve results and how we do it. And here, in my opinion, is the main confusion: the alternative attitude to personalized education as a set of modalities or as a set of desired outcomes.

It is not only about the availability of technology in the learning model. Instead of this individual education describes the combination of methods and goals in this area. that will achieve the best results for students. Blended learning is often one such method, as the use of certain types of online learning tends to personalize learning to the point where it is more convenient for a single instructor who serves multiple students with varying levels of knowledge and skills. Depending on the results of the individual education which is covered by the relevant system, models and the content of blended education can be radically different.

Blended learning in a study group should be dynamic, fun and flexible. This technology is purposefully incorporated into a broader curriculum where personalization is a priority. [3]

Blended learning requires specific digital competencies, whereas educators should create online courses, determine them for students, track their progress and etc. Some e-learning tools have a steep learning curve and not all teachers may be willing to invest the time and effort required to master a new technology tool.

According to the research of scientists, six different reasons are indicated of implementation of blended learning: “pedagogical richness, access to knowledge, social interaction, personal participation, cost-effectiveness and ease of revision.”

Theoretical materials can be difficult (if not boring). It is one thing for students to sit and listen to a lecturer for hours, and another thing for them to learn the same information by pushing buttons, participating in a tax simulation, taking a game course, etc. Blended learning leads to greater involvement of medical students, providing various opportunities and using digital tools.

An online lecture is an educational lecture designed to be published on the Internet. Lectures are recorded on video, audio or both, and then recorded and submitted for viewing on a dedicated site. Students can go to a certain website and watch an online lecture in their spare time. The lecture can be viewed online in real time during filming.

In traditional teaching, a lecture is possible only when the teacher and the student are in the same room, while the lecturer transmits information to the copper student in close proximity. Development of online lectures ensures that the teacher and student no longer need to be around to teach and learn properly.

Online lectures have certain advantages. Students have access to online lectures hosted on their website anywhere in the world and at any time convenient for them, provided they have an internet connection. They can also be repeated when writing notes. Research has shown that students significantly improve their course skills with online archived lectures. Research has also shown that students' overall perception of the course has improved with the addition of online lectures. Online learning can also be one of the solutions to balance the education of medical students. Online lectures also have drawbacks, namely the lack of face-to-face communication and the fact that students cannot easily contact their teachers unless a line of communication is established. In addition, class attendance may be reduced due to recorded lectures.

The role of the lecture in higher education has been questioned for some time, although it is still a common means of conveying knowledge. [6] The lecture was heavily criticized due to its predominantly one-pointed nature and inefficiency.

Blended learning allows students to watch lectures at their own pace and time, making the process more efficient and accessible for everyone.

Lectures are presented as a less popular alternative to blended learning. Apparently, the two advantages claimed by the technology are not enough to make lectures more attractive than the more complete blended learning.

A convenient and easy way to engage audience is group work. Group discussions discuss controversial issue, problems, a kind of dispute aimed at achieving the truth and using only the correct methods of arguing. Knowledge, acquired through practice, are fixed better. [5] Their value is higher due to the fact that a person comes to them not through observation, but through independent action. One advantage of online discussions, which sometimes refers to, is letting shy group members become more willing to participate in the discussion. However, evidence has also been found that some students feel similarly overwhelmed when participating in online discussions [4]. Group discussions teach teamwork: one of the most important skills for medical students ensures maximum involvement: even if the participant does not actively interact with the group, the concentration of attention on the webinar with team activities will be higher, it forms a comfortable psychological climate in learning, the possibility of attracting students from other pears and even universities.

At present, there are three modes in pedagogical teaching and learning, namely, normal offline mode, online only mode, and mixed mode of online and offline teaching and learning. Larson and Sun (2009) demonstrated that there were no significant differences between these three modes. However, mixed and online modes received particularly high marks by indicators

"satisfaction of students, learning efficiency, satisfaction of teachers." Yen and etc.(2018) conducted a three-way comparison of face-to-face, online, and blended learning modes in a child development course for students. They found that online activities can be as effective as face-to-face sessions in achieving satisfactory. However, blended mode has great potential to improve student academic performance by integrating the benefits of both face-to-face and online learning.[7] Similarly, a recent study by Yu et al.(2021) found that both blended and offline learning are effective educational approaches to improve the critical thinking ability of medical students, while the use of blended medical professionals to critical thinking, while the use of case-based blended learning has shown promising results in improving student achievement.

Effective teaching has always been and remains student-centered; whatever strategy you choose, you can't go wrong putting your students above everything else and then optimizing the rest as you go. [1]

LITERATURE:

1. Yuhong Jiang, Yingying Chen, Jiasheng Lu and Yiqing Wang* The Effect of the Online and Offline Blended Teaching Mode on English as a Foreign Language Learners' Listening Performance in a Chinese Context *Front. Psychol.*, 16 November 2021 Sec. Educational Psychology <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.742742>
2. McGraw Hill Blended Learning: Strategies for Implementation Oct 24, 2017 <https://medium.com/inspired-ideas-prek-12/blended-learning-strategies-for-implementation-8e86e9349ac7>
3. Komilova, M. (2022). Methods of increasing the level of cognitive activity of students when implementing mixed forms in medical education.
4. Komilova, M. O., & Роль, I. F. критерии эффективности системы смешанного обучения студентов. Komilova M. O, Iskandjanova FK Xalq ta'limi, 6.
5. Комилова, М. О. (2016). Касб танлаш, касбга йўналтириш муаммоларининг ўзбек психологлари томонидан ўрганилганлиги. In Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера (No. 6, pp. 8-9). Vedecko vydavateľské centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.
6. Исканджанова, Ф. К. (2022). МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНО ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ И ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ ВРАЧА-ПЕДАГОГА: Исканджанова Феруза Камолдиновна, Преподаватель кафедры «Педагогика и психология» Ташкентская медицинская академия. Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (6.2. Махсус сон), 163-166.
7. Комилова, М. О. (2022). СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ И РАЗВИТИЕ СМЕШАННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ: Комилова Малохат Олимовна, Старший преподаватель Ташкентской медицинской академии. Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (6), 119-121.
8. Комилова, М. О. (2022). ПОДХОДЫ «РОТАЦИЯ СТАНЦИЙ» В СМЕШАННОМ ОБУЧЕНИИ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 23, 347-350.
9. Комилова, М. О. (2022, August). ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЕ СМЕШАННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ: Комилова Малохат Олимовна, Ташкентская медицинская академия Кафедра педагогики и психологии, старший преподаватель malokhat.komilova@mail.ru. In Научно-практическая конференция.